

Thermal Decomposition of Barium and Mercury(II) Nitrate

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The progress of decomposition of anhyd. barium and mercury (II) nitrates, as revealed by the chemical analyses of the products formed at different stages between the beginning and end of the decomposition and at equilibrium, has shown the formation of a basic nitrate, $2\text{HgO} \cdot \text{Hg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, by the mercury salt as an intermediate before ultimately forming mercury (II) oxide, nitrogen dioxide and oxygen. The barium salt forms appreciable quantities of nitrite and oxygen before forming the final products which are the same as in the case of the mercury salt. In the atmosphere of nitric oxide both the nitrate form nitrite at temperatures lower than their normal decomposition temperatures.

Chemical analysis of the products of thermal decomposition at various stages between the beginning and end of the decomposition is, perhaps, the only direct method of establishing intermediate compound formation and instrumental methods such as the analysis of the X-ray and infra-red spectra should be regarded as supplementing the results obtained primarily by the classical methods of chemical analysis. In the case of the nitrates of barium and mercury, the heavy elements of the second group—the S-block and the D-block—the results are not published¹. The results are of intrinsic importance as affording clue to the understanding of the ultimate nature of such compounds. Gordon and Campbell² reported DTA studies of the thermal reactions of anhyd. barium nitrate and of mercury(II) nitrate hemihydrate (fusion points 588° and 145° respectively): the alkaline earth nitrates underwent no crystalline transitions but showed large endothermal dip accompanying rapid evolution of nitrous fumes while the mercury nitrate indicated many endotherms, the last one beyond 350° being due to refluxing mercury. Field and Hardy³ observed that the results of DTA studies need to be interpreted with caution and may best be used to substantiate the results of the classical or/and infra-red studies.

The present paper describes the results obtained by the classical method. In the opinion of one of the authors (TMO), ultimately this method alone can establish the results obtained by the X-ray, infra-red etc. methods and the latter methods may be used only to enhance the value obtained directly. The physico-chemical methods cannot replace the classical methods of chemical analysis.

Another interest about these studies is that the mercury(II) salt is, like the copper salt, bidentate⁴ and has a lower oxidation state (see ref. 5) and it decomposes like the nitrates of zinc and cadmium (the latter of which is described as fully ionic) at a much lower temperature (only 160°). The mercury(II) nitrate is found, in this work to form basic

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2. S. Gordon and C. Campbell, *Anal. Chem.*, 1955, **27**, 1102.
3. B. O. Field and C. J. Hardy, *Quart. Rev.*, 1964, **18**, 361-88.
4. R. E. Lavilla and S. B. Bauer., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **85**, 3597.

nitrate and nitrite is formed only in traces unlike the barium salt which decomposes at 550° forming appreciable quantities of nitrite. A comparison of mercury (II) nitrate with lead nitrate⁶ is also interesting.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials: Barium nitrate was A. R. quality (B.D.H.) recrystallized and dried to constant weight. Found: Ba, 52.6; NO₃, 47.3 percent. Ba(NO₃)₂ requires Ba, 52.55; NO₃, 47.45 percent. Mercury(II) nitrate was made by the action of pure nitric acid on mercury (II) oxide and precipitated by adding fuming nitric acid. It was left in a desiccator over KOH sticks and dried over P₂O₅ in a vacuum desiccator. Found: Hg, 62.2; NO₃, 37.8 percent. Hg(NO₃)₂ requires Hg, 62.2, NO₃, 38.2 percent. Pure nitric oxide was made by heating silver nitrite⁷. Analyses of the products was done as in references 8 and 9. To study the action of nitric oxide the apparatus shown in Fig. 1, ref. 10 was used. Otherwise the apparatus was as in ref. 9. Presence of nitrite in the decomposition products of mercury (II) nitrate was tested for by triturating the residue with aq. KOH and applying the test to the filtrate: acidified permanganate got discoloured.

Results: Table I shows the results of heating 0.25 g barium nitrate at the temperatures stated. The decomposition was noticed even at 525° but was slow upto 550°: nitrite was indicated in the products even at 525° but being unstable at the temperature⁸, a part of it must have decomposed. The table shows that the ratio, nitrite formed to nitrate consumed, is 0.92 and of oxide formed to nitrate consumed is 0.14 while the ratio of nitrogen dioxide to oxygen is only 1.7 at the end of 1 hr. at 525°; further that these ratios change rapidly at 550°. Fig. 1 shows at a glance the formation of oxygen and accumulation of nitrite at the start of the decomposition. Table II shows the results for mercury (II) nitrate (0.3 g) at 160° and 220° at the end of 1, 2 and 3 hrs. and at 300° at the end of 2 hrs. Here appreciable decomposition is seen even at 160° in 1 hr. since the ratio of mercury(II) oxide to mercury

TABLE I

Effect of temperature on the thermal decomposition of 0.250 g. barium nitrate in 1 hr.

Temp. °C	Solid Residue: g.			Gaseous Products: ml.						
	Ba (NO ₃) ₂	Ba (NO ₂) ₂	BaO	NO ₂	O ₂	N ₂	Ba(NO ₃) ₂ consumed 10 ⁻⁵	Ba(NO ₂) ₂ Ba(NO ₃) ₂	BaO Ba(NO ₃) ₂	O ₂
525**	0.2431	0.00508 (2.2)	—	0.56	0.43	—	690 (2.6)	1.3
525	0.2405	0.00750 (3.3)	0.00076 (0.5)	0.98	0.57	0.1	950 (3.6)	0.92	0.14	1.7
550	0.2205	0.00780 (3.5)	0.01377 (9.0)	7.5	1.9	0.3	2900 (11.3)	0.304	0.82	3.9
575	0.1415	0.01433 (6.24)	0.5412 (35.3)	15.9	4.2	0.4	10850 (41.5)	0.1502	0.85	3.8
625	0.00980	0.00186 (0.812)	0.13910 (91.05)	39.3	10.3	0.7	24020 (91.9)	0.0084	0.99	3.8

**The decomposition was arrested at 30 mts. in this experiment.
Parentheses show the amounts of the substance in the column as gm. mol. 10⁻⁵.

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6. P. Vrantray and P. Gugliotta, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1963, **25**, 1129.
7. T. M. Oza, R. H. Thaker and V. T. Oza, *J. Chem., Soc.*, 1955, 2457.
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(II) nitrate in the products formed is about 1. In 2 and 3 hrs. the value of the ratio increases. At 220° however, the value of the ratio is 1.9 to 2.0, almost constant at the end of 1,2 or 3 hrs, the equilibrium stage being attained. The tendency thus seems to attain to the

FIG. 1

composition $\text{HgO} \cdot \text{Hg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, a compound reported in the reaction of mercury (II) nitrate with the hydroxide ion¹². It may be pointed out that a similar basic compound $\text{HgO} \cdot \text{HgNO}_3$ is also reported in the thermal decomposition of mercury (I) nitrate, both hydrated and anhydrous, by Myers¹³. The compound, $\text{HgO} \cdot \text{Hg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, will, evidently, be not very stable and this is indicated at 300° where the value of the ratio increases. Simultaneously the

TABLE II

Formation of basic nitrate in the decomposition of 0.3 g mercury(II) nitrate.

Temp. °C	Period of heating: hr	Residue: g		
		$\text{Hg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$	HgO	$\frac{\text{HgO}}{\text{Hg}(\text{NO}_3)_2}$
160	1	0.1598 (49.2)	0.1070 (49.4)	1.005
"	2	0.1342 (47.7)	0.1433 (64.7)	1.3
"	3	0.1316 (43.2)	0.1433 (64.7)	1.3
220	1	0.1285 (39.6)	0.1651 (74.8)	1.9
"	2	0.1271 (39.1)	0.1679 (77.5)	1.98
"	3	0.1262 (38.9)	0.1685 (77.8)	2.0
300	2	0.1055 (32.5)	0.1791 (82.7)	2.54

Parentheses show the quantities in g. mol 10^{-5} .

residue which was pale yellow at 220° became red at 300° as by the formation of mercury

9. T. M. Oza and (Miss) E. I. Ezekiel., *J. Sci. & Indus. Res.*, 1962, **21B**, 536.
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11. T. M. Oza and V. T. Oza, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 907.
12. R. B. Bernstein, H. G. Pars and D. C. Blumenthal, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **79**, 1574.
13. Myers, *Proc. K. Akad. Wetenscg. Amsterdam*, 1902, **4**, 637,

(II) oxide. Table III shows the analysis of the entire system present at cessation of the decomposition i.e., at the equilibrium stage, when initially 0.1, 0.2 and 0.3 g mercury(II) nitrate was taken and heated at 200° until no bubble formation was indicated for some time in the aq. KOH trap in the apparatus. The ratio mercury(II) oxide to mercury(II) nitrate in the residues approaches 2 here also as in the relevant results of Table II. The ratio of nitrogen dioxide to oxygen is about 4. As the ratio mercury(II) oxide formed to mercury (II) nitrate consumed is the same in all the experiments the decomposition has the characteristic of a homogeneous reaction.

TABLE III

Composition of residue and gas at cessation of decomposition in the decomposition of mercury (II) nitrate at 200° with different initial masses.

Mass of Hg (NO ₃) ₂ : g	Residue: g		HgO	Hg (NO ₃) ₂	Hgo formed	Gas : ml		NO ₂
	Hg (NO ₃) ₂	HgO	Hg(NO ₃) ₂	consumed:g	Hg(NO ₃) ₂ consumed	NO ₂	O ₂	O ₂
0.1000	0.0345 (10.6)	0.041 (19.0)	1.8	0.065	0.63	3.2	0.8	4.0
0.2000	0.0717 (22.2)	0.083 (38.4)	1.75	0.128	0.64	7.2	1.7	4.2
0.3000	0.1026	0.1280	1.9	0.197	0.65	9.1	2.4	3.8

Parentheses in tables II and III show g. mol. 10⁻⁵.

Table IV gives the results of heating the anhydrous nitrates under the atmosphere of nitric oxide. Nitric oxide was stored at 80.0 mm. mercury pressure. The results show that barium nitrate forms nitrite at 375° in 1 hr. and that the quantities of nitrite increase at 475° and 500° —at the latter temperature a part of the nitrite formed will decompose and this is indicated by the presence of barium oxide in the products. In the case of mercury (II) nitrate, the action of nitric oxide is observed even at 50° since both nitrite and nitrogen

TABLE IV

Action of nitric oxide atmosphere (press. 80.0 mm. Hg) on barium nitrate and mercury (II) nitrate.

<i>Barium nitrate</i> (mass 0.250 g.)—			
Temp. °C	Time: hr.	Nitrite formed 10 ⁻⁴ g.	NO ₂ formed: ml
375	1	(barium) trace	—
400	1	8.5	—
475	½	15.3	—
„	1	39.3	—
500	1	49.3	1.25
„	2	50.3	1.3
„	7	28.6*	5.9
<i>Mercury (II) nitrate</i> (mass. 1.0 g.)—			
50	½	165.00	1.5
70**	„	„	3.00
90	„	191.00	3.9
110	„	239.00	6.00

*97×10⁻⁴ g. barium oxide was found present along with the nitrite showing that some of the nitrite formed had decomposed.

**Mercury (II) nitrite tends to be unstable at and above this temperature.

dioxide were found present in the system at the end of $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. only. Rise of temperature has however no conspicuous effect on the mercury salt and this behaviour of the mercury salt may hence be ascribed to the partial ionic character of the salt, as the barium salt—ionic—forms appreciable amounts of nitrite.

The results given above along with those on the thermal decomposition of barium nitrite⁸ and of mercury(II) nitrite⁹ show that the ionic barium nitrate forms nitrite and oxygen in the primary stage of the decomposition while the covalent mercury(II) nitrate forms only some nitrite by virtue of its partial ionic character but passes mainly into the basic nitrate. The question why the ionic and covalent nitrates behave in this way needs more data on other nitrates for the understanding. It is the property of the metal atom present and the complex-forming property of the D-orbitals will be at work in the case of the mercury salt. Barium(II) nitrite and mercury(II) nitrite are studied by Oza and the co-workers^{8,9}: the final products are similar in either case but this might be due to the comparatively greater instability of the mercury salt and when formed from the nitrate, it will readily decompose being in a different energy state. The decomposition of lead(II) nitrate is studied by infra-red analysis⁶. As the oxidatin state of mercury remains two as of lead, it is not unlikely that the composition of the basic nitrates formed from the mercury salt may be passing progressively from $\text{HgO.Hg(NO}_3)_2$ to $2\text{HgO.Hg(NO}_3)_2 \dots n\text{HgO.(n-1)Hg(NO}_3)_2$ before finally passing into Hg(II)O .

As both the nitrites behave similarly in giving the same products of the decomposition and the nitrates behave differently, it is obvious that the difference lies in the nitrate-forming oxygen atom. Three anhydrous nitrates have been studied so far by Oza and the co-workers for their behaviour under the atmosphere of nitric oxide. Anhyd. magnesium nitrate, largely ionic, decomposes in vacuo at 350° ¹⁴ forming nitrite and in the nitric oxide atmosphere at 130° forming nitrite which (latter) decomposes at 110° ¹⁵; anhyd. mercury(II) nitrate decomposes in vacuo, as found in this work, at 160° forming little nitrite and largely basic nitrate and decomposes as early as at 50° in the atmosphere of nitric oxide to form nitrite. Barium nitrate behaves similarly to the magnesium salt, the nitrite formed in the atmosphere of nitric oxide increasing in amount with rise of temperature. Further reduction to hyponitrite does not occur in the atmosphere of nitric oxide and more than one oxygen atom per molecule is not eliminated. Reduction to hyponitrite does occur with charcoal¹⁶ and both sodium nitrate and sodium nitrite are reduced to hyponitrite by sodium amalgam¹⁷. These facts show that the bonds forming nitrate from nitrite and those forming nitrite from hyponitrite are of varying strengths. The facts that (1) hyponitrites do not become oxidized to nitrite¹⁸ quantitatively and (2) nitrites do become so oxidized, point also to the same view.

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